

Iterative Body Synthesis

Investigating Algorithmic Agency in Social Media Body Representations

Michael Wallinger

Independent Artist

Vienna Austria

info@michaelwallinger.net

ABSTRACT

This Work-in-Progress (WiP) paper introduces ITERATIVE BODY SYNTHESIS, a media installation that acts as both a research infrastructure for an experimental online investigation and a neural backend and monitoring interface for a virtual identity on Instagram. The project aims to investigate the impact of algorithmic decision-making on body representations in social media, exploring how these platforms may shape and distort forms of representation and perception such as body aesthetics, choreography, iconography, and authenticity.

Given the opacity of this social media platform, ITERATIVE BODY SYNTHESIS is conceptualised as an infrastructure for a distributed monitoring. It is implemented through an incremental development process akin to adaptive black box testing methodologies, enabling us to navigate the research landscape without prior knowledge of the inner workings of the systems under investigation. To this end, we have developed a prototype of a self-operating software architecture based on principles of black box testing, machine learning, and synthetic data.

Social media platforms like Instagram treat their users as black boxes, analysing their affects based on continuously sampled visual media. By reversing this practice and identifying algorithmic "affects" towards specific body characteristics, we cast a virtual hyper-embodiment of Instagram's affective economies and notions of integrity. With this, ITERATIVE BODY SYNTHESIS explores technological possibilities for developing a digital infrastructure that empowers citizens to collectively monitor algorithmic systems that moderate, filter, and verify our media realities.

KEYWORDS

Synthetic Data, Black Box Testing, Social Media, Machine Learning, Iterative Body Synthesis

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Figure 1: ITERATIVE BODY SYNTHESIS, 2022. Michael Wallinger, server unit, projection (monitoring interface), screen (video documentation). ©M. Wallinger.

1 Introduction

META's platforms, Facebook and Instagram, have spearheaded the exploitation of automated content recognition and verification systems, affective computing technologies such as emotion recognition and behavioural biometrics, as well as highly precise personalisation algorithms across a broad user base. They leverage a complex ensemble of advanced machine learning techniques to detect platform violations and to rank and moderate content. This moderation recommends or restricts content to optimise user engagement and dwell time. With their proprietary and intricate architectures, these recommendation systems operate as black boxes that obscure their decision-making processes from public monitoring.

Simultaneously, these systems are known to contribute to the amplification of seductive and polarising content as well as to an over-representation of visual media promoting illusionary body ideals. With such a prospect of positive reinforcement in terms of visibility and attention, these systems also encourage users to produce similar content and thus have a profound impact on our viewing habits and content production, affecting how we perceive and understand the world and ourselves. However, these implications are not limited to the area of communication and media consumption directly on these platforms, which undoubtedly have a significant effect on our mental health and autonomy.

Increasingly, data scraped from social media platforms is being integrated into new technologies that, as data-driven systems, tend to amplify the biases and misrepresentations present in their data sets. As a result, such algorithmic and corporate decision-making on what is relevant and what is redundant become inscribed in these datasets as biasing over- and under-representations. Consequently, they reappear discretely in software-based sensor enhancements in apps, smartphones and cameras; in motion capture software and other body and pose synthesis systems; in avatar models in game engines and virtual environments; and in technologies for generative text, image and video production and their multimodal integrations. This, in turn, might have a significant impact on our future everyday lives and cultural production.

To analyse the influence of Algorithmic agency on the over- and under-representation of body images on social media platforms, conventional black box testing methods, reliant on input-output relations, fall short in providing insights into these intricate, dynamic, and adaptive systems that curate content to individual user profiles. Information on Instagram's internal structure is limited to vague descriptions provided by the platform and rather speculative assessments from the outside based on similar technologies and experiences by users and creators. Given these conditions and the fact that the input-output relationships of these systems are different for each user, we have conceptualised ITERATIVE BODY SYNTHESIS as an infrastructure for a distributed monitoring, which, inspired by adaptive black-box testing methods, is developed in an incremental, iterative process (Figure 2). This allows us to gradually approach the conditions of the research landscape without having to rely on unverified hypotheses. In this way, we aim to develop a software system in compliance with data protection guidelines and ethical considerations that enables black box testing and cross-referencing of individual user environments via data donations. We developed a prototype based on principles of black box testing (Figure 2), machine learning, and synthetic data and integrated it into an installation, consisting of a server unit, a monitoring interface, and contextualising video documentation (Figure 1).

2 Hyper-Embodiment

The conceptualisation and representational method of hyper-embodiment originated from speculative inquiries into emotion recognition, affective computing, behavioural biometrics, and generative technologies, alongside their dystopian potential for behavioural and social engineering practices, and emotional contagion. This concept provides a compelling framework for examining questions of accountability regarding algorithmic agency and its implications for our mental autonomy and health, as well as the profound influence of these technologies on shaping viewing habits, norms, and the broader social fabric. Artistically implemented as a kind of virtual performance of continuous body transformations, our aim is to shift the focus from the network utopian notion of disembodiment [e.g.: 1,2,3] as a retreat from

realities and their social relations of violence to a discourse on algorithmically enhanced hyper-embodiment.

Figure 2: Basic principle of adaptive black box testing: External analysis of a system without knowledge of its inner workings by gradually adapting inputs based on previous input-output relations.

3 ITERATIVE BODY SYNTHESIS

ITERATIVE BODY SYNTHESIS simultaneously acts as a live evaluating research infrastructure, a monitoring interface, and a neural backend for a virtual identity on Instagram. In a feedback-loop communication between the installation and Instagram, the appearance and choreography of the virtual body converge to the most consistent patterns between body characteristics and online in-/visibility, thus creating a kind of virtual performance of continuous body transformations.

Our black box testing approach employs a feedback-driven sampling strategy, iteratively refining new sample sequences to pose increasingly informative visual queries to the algorithmically personalised user environments (Figure 2). This iterative process allows us to calibrate the visual composition of new samples towards indicators for causalities between body characteristics and algorithmic decision-making, while continuously reassessing them.

An auto-evaluating sampling algorithm correlates body characteristics, body pose, hand pose, body proportion, and facial expression with each other and with Instagram's algorithmic distribution. Using this information, it coordinates the outputs of multiple artificial neural networks to generate the next sequence of body transformations. In daily iteration cycles, these sequences are rendered, automatically shared on Instagram, and the ranking signals and audience reach metrics of previous sample sequences

are collected for the subsequent cycle. In addition, we repeat a variation of this process for cross-referencing with the account of another virtual identity whose sensitive body parts are censored. In this way, with each iteration, recurring consistencies and patterns of algorithmic decision-making inscribe themselves more deeply into the appearance and movement of the virtual body, allowing a canon of algorithmic amplification and limitation to be identified.

Figure 3: ITERATIVE BODY SYNTHESIS, 2022. Michael Wallinger, still (video documentation). ©M. Wallinger.

3.1 Synthetic Body Representation

Our approach adopts the use of synthetic data to address the challenges associated with analysing user-generated content on platforms like Instagram, which, although vast, present substantial ethical, methodological, and practical limitations. Direct analysis of real user-generated content would necessitate invasive biometric measurements, susceptible to distortion by various factors such as camera angles, clothing, and poses, thereby introducing significant noise. Moreover, this approach would raise considerable data protection concerns and restrict the reusability of the data for further studies due to privacy issues.

Alternatively, while the adaptation of body synthesis models could mitigate some distortions by fitting standardised virtual bodies into real-world body images, these models also introduce their own set of inaccuracies and biases. Consequently, to overcome these limitations and enable direct and self-referential comparability of body characteristics, as well as standardisation, our method utilises synthetic data modelled according to the SMPL-X notation [4]. This standard in human body and motion synthesis tasks in computer science not only eliminates the ethical dilemmas of handling personal and biometric data but also facilitates the creation of a controlled, replicable dataset that can be permanently stored and shared across studies.

However, it is important to acknowledge that while synthetic data aids in achieving exact comparability and alleviates privacy concerns, it is based on statistical models, and thus bound to means and deviations, inherently abstracting from reality to become representative. Therefore, it may not fully capture the diversity of real bodies, motions, and poses that exist outside of the limited range of the average body modelled from their data sets. Despite these trade-offs, the approach allows for ethical

research practices and contributes to a more sustainable and shareable body of research data.

3.2 Sampling & Evaluation

As mentioned above, we derived our approach and ambitions from black box testing methodologies (Figure 2), meaning that we aim to gradually explore the inner workings of Instagram without relying on assessments or speculations based on similar technologies or anecdotal evidence from users. It is freely observable and also overtly communicated by Instagram that user interactions, such as comments, likes, saves, and shares, are signals that contribute to the higher ranking of a particular post or similar content [5].

To investigate whether content with similar user interactions is displayed at varying frequencies in user feeds, indicating a possible correlation between visual content composition and algorithmic decision-making, we developed a novel auto-evaluating sampling algorithm. This algorithm determines the similarity of our content samples and analyses whether the ratio of user engagement to the reach of a particular composition of body characteristics differs from those of other compositions. For this purpose, it agglomeratively clusters all previously sampled body characteristics based on their similarity and examines the coherence between content ranking signals and the audience reach of each sample. Specifically, we represent body characteristics such as body pose, body shape, hand pose, and facial expression as high-dimensional vectors (66, 10, 45, and 10 dimensions respectively, per frame), enabling us to apply cosine similarity to precisely determine how similar one body representation is to another (Figure 3). Through this method, we compare each individual sampled body characteristic against all others. This enables us to cluster highly similar body characteristics across different sample sequences or iterations, allowing for a detailed assessment of whether specific body characteristics exhibit a consistent engagement-to-reach ratio while also distinguishing them from the engagement-to-reach ratios of other body characteristics. If we identify a cluster with high coherence whose engagement-to-reach ratio differs from that of other clusters, we consider it an indicator of possible algorithmic bias. We then extract a key body characteristic from this cluster and use it as a new target position for the next iteration cycle to re-evaluate it. This evaluation process is not only sensitive to outliers and singleton clusters, i.e., clusters that consist of a single data point and therefore always have maximum coherence with themselves; it also continuously re-evaluates currently identified consistencies and deviations. In this way, the process successively refines itself while simultaneously enhancing the distribution and coverage of the sampling space.

3.3 Body & Motion Synthesis

The selected key body characteristics guide the transformations of the virtual body, which are generated by specialised transformer and autoencoder models. For the task of human motion synthesis, namely the generation of poses and movements, we trained these

models with the AMASS dataset [6]. For body shape transformations, we have used both the AMASS and the AGORA datasets [7].

Based on the seminal architectures for transformer [8] and autoencoder [9] models, we designed these artificial neural networks to perform an in-betweening task, predicting transitions from a seed sequence to a target position. In the case of the transformer architecture, which we use for hand movements, we have developed an autoregressive transformer-decoder model that iteratively generates frames or positions within a deep neural network. The autoencoder model for body motion follows a masked approach. This involves inserting a mask between the seed sequence and the target position, where the entire sequence is generated at once by encoding the masked sequence into a lower-dimensional latent space and then decoding it back to the original dimensionality.

In this process of progressing from a seed sequence to a target position, new intermediate positions are introduced with each new sample composition. This constantly expands the variance of the sampling space with additional data points of body characteristics. Thus, the distribution and coverage of possible positions in the sampling space are enhanced, whereby the analysis gradually refines itself and the appearance and movement of the virtual body are continuously calibrated towards algorithmic prioritisations and discriminations.

4 Preliminary Results

Our initial phase of data collection resulted in a robust dataset from two different virtual user environments, compiling 463 sample sequences along with corresponding ranking signals and audience reach data. This dataset includes approximately 1,361 different body poses, 2,580 different hand poses, 10,985 different facial expressions, and 3,492 different body shapes.

Throughout the project, we encountered several unexpected challenges that provided additional insights. One notable issue was the phenomenon of shadow banning, where our virtual identity's account was blocked within the first week of sampling. Although reactivation was possible, the reach of our samples was notably restricted thereafter. Additionally, the virtual body was frequently classified as nude, which led to further restrictions impacting our data collection. To address this, we initiated a second account with an identical virtual identity but with sensitive body parts censored.

We also observed that Instagram's variance in content guidelines or spam filters limited our ability to conduct a controlled experiment with highly similar visual content, hashtags, and captions. Initially, we established small enclosed networks of fake accounts to follow our virtual identity, intended as a control group for network and visibility analyses. However, these fake accounts were deleted within two weeks, complicating our efforts to analyse ongoing engagement between accounts.

Despite these challenges, our data intriguingly suggests that engagement and reach do not correlate in a direct or linear

fashion, indicating the presence of additional impact factors. According to Instagram, these include specifics of the post itself, such as the visual content of the post and its metadata, information about the posting account, and the engagement history with other accounts [5].

5 Future Perspectives & Next Steps

Looking forward, our project will focus on monitoring the overall engagement history and additional data about our account, such as follower count and interaction frequency, to refine our evaluations further. Currently, we are integrating the TikTok API and transitioning our render pipeline to a diffusion model. Consequently, we are developing a customized ControlNet that will harness the photorealistic and flexible potential of diffusion models for generating and evaluating 3D body data. These steps aim to enhance our methodological framework in order to gain more detailed insights into the algorithmic agency that determines the visibility of bodies.

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